

Ethnobotanical Survey In Different Mandals Of Adilabad District, Andhra Pradesh, India

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Abstract

Ethno botanical surveys were conducted from October, 2011 through September, 2012 in the Jannaram, Kaddam, Utnoor and Indravelly, mandals of Adilabad district, Andhra Pradesh, India. Information on 40 angiosperms belonging to 24 families was gathered with regard to their ethno medicinal plants used by the tribal people in alleviating diseases. The medicinal plants used by local tribal traditional healers are arranged alphabetically followed by botanical name, family names, local name, parts used, mode of preparation and medicinal uses. This paper reports for the uses of plant parts by the tribal people in the form of juices, extracts, decoctions, pastes and powders.

Keywords: Ethno medicines, Adilabad district, tribal people, Andhra Pradesh.

INTRODUCTION

Plants are the basis of life on earth and are central to people's livelihoods. Tribal people are the ecosystem people who live in harmony with the nature and maintain a close link between man and environment. (V. Madhu and C. Suvatha. 2009; Madhu and Rajesh, 2011). Indian subcontinent is being inhabited by over 53.8 million tribal people in 5000 forest dominated villages of tribal community and comprising 15% of the total geographical area of Indian landmasses, representing one of the greatest emporia of ethno-botanical wealth. (Albert L, Sajem and Kuldip Gosai 2006). The ethno botanical survey can bring out many different clues for the development of drugs to treat human diseases. (Ghosh A 2003) India has great relationship with Ethnobotany from the ancient times as in India medicinal plants have been used in India traditional systems of medicine namely Ayurveda and Siddha from immemorial days. (Mubeen, *et al*, 2005; Madhu and Swamy, 2010) India has one of world's richest floras besides centuries of old experienced practices. Now in India herbal medicines occupy a valuable sector for health care system and medicinal plants represents a major economic resource. In this page, we report on the information gathered from tribal on the plants used for treatment of various diseases in tribal areas of Adilabad District, Andhra Pradesh, India. (Pullaiah, et al, 1992; Madhu and Suvatha, 2009)

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study Area

The study area is depicted in fig-1. Adilabad district lies between $77^{\circ} 47'$ and $80^{\circ} 0'$ of the eastern longitudes and $18^{\circ} 40'$ and $19^{\circ} 56'$ of northern latitudes. The district is bounded on North by Yeotmal, on the East by Chanda districts of Maharashtra and on the South by Karimnagar and Nizamabad and on the West by Nanded district of Maharashtra

State. These harbour mainly dry deciduous forest and aborigines. These forests occupy about 44.5 percent of the total geographical area of the district. The total forest area in the district is 7218.86 sq.km. The total population of the district is 27, 37, 738 out of which the tribal population is 5,12,602 (Census of India 2011). Among scheduled tribes of Andhra Pradesh, Gonds, Lambada, Kolams, Pradhans, Manne, Naikpods, Thoties, Yerikalas, Koyas are the major communities in Adilabad District, Andhra Pradesh, India.

Ethnobotanical Survey

Field trips were conducted from October, 2011 through September, 2012 in tribal parts of Jannaram, Kaddam, Utnoor and Indravelli, mandals Adilabad district, Andhra Pradesh, India. Ethnomedicinal data were collected through conversation with traditional healers', tribal doctors and elder people in the field trips. During the interviews local names, useful plant parts, method of preparation and dosage were recorded (Table 1). The method of collection of voucher specimens, preservation, herbaria and technique for the collection of Ethnomedicinal information's follows Jain and Rao (1977). Herbarium Voucher specimens are deposited at Kakatiya University, Warangal, Andhra Pradesh, India. The plant species are enumerated by family followed by their tribal names and uses.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In the present account, 40 species of angiosperms belonging to 25 families are reported (Table 1). They are used as ethnomedicines for various severe diseases like jaundice, cancer, etc. by employing the preparations in the form of extracts, pastes, juices, powders, etc. Other common diseases and health complaints like Abortion, Anti inflammations, Asthma, Arthritis, Blood Pressure, Blood Bleeding, Cough, Diabetes, Dandruff, Diarrhea, Fertility improvement of male, Fever, Filaria, Hepatitis, Jaundice, Kidney disease, Ladies White Discharges, Muscular Pains, Pains, Paralysis, Ring Worm, Sugar, Scorpion Bite, Skin Allergy, Stomach Pain, Skin Diseases, STD's, Snake Bite, Tooth ache, Wound healing are cured by using of various plants found in the tribal healers of Adilabad district .

The plant material is employed in the form of decoctions, extracts, pastes, juice&Powder some times in combination with other parts of same or different plants other substances, such as sugar candy, curd, honey, hair oil, milk and turmeric powder, are also used in various preparations. The data collected from the tribal people of Adilabad district pertaining to the treatment of various ailments by Plant parts used for medicinal preparation were bark, roots, leaves, fruits, flowers, Stem, seeds and the whole plants. The most frequently utilized plant parts percentage were leaves (52.5%), followed by the roots (17.5%), seeds (3%), Stem bark (10%) fruits (12.5%), Stem (2.5%) flowers (3%), in the form of decoctions, extracts, paste, juices and powders (Fig-2).

The medicinal plants based on their use in treatment of 30 different diseases were found to be very valuable such as Jaundice, asthma, diabetes, STD's, paralysis, snake bite, Fever . Among the different plant parts used for the preparation of medicine the leaves were the most important and frequently used and majority of the remedies reported in the present study are by administering the leaves orally.

The most dominant families of ethnobotanical importance are Fabaceae (4 species), Asclepiadaceae (4 species), Amaranthaceae (3 species), Asteraceae (3 species),

Leguminoceae (3 species), Euphorbiaceae (2 species), Solanaceae (2 species), Phyllanthaceae (2 species), Lamiaceae (2 species), Simaroubaceae (1 species), Agavaceae (1 species), Aristolochiaceae (1 species), Meliaceae (1 species), Graminae (1 species), Rutaceae (1 species), Moraceae (1 species), Cucurbitaceae (1 species), Morigaceae (1 species), Bignoniaceae (1 species), Rosaceae (1 species), Combritaceae (1 species), Menispermaceae (1 species), Aizoaceae (1 species), Zygophylliaceae (1 species) and Zingibaraceae (1 species). In the present study percentage of remedies using for different disessea as shown in figure 3. Traditional healers of Adilabad district used 8 species to treat body pain relief, 6 species to treat skin diseases and other for different problems like jaundice, STDs, female genital problems , fever, poisonous bites , diabetes etc.

CONCLUSION

The present investigation revealed that medicinal plants still play a vital role in the primary health care of the people. The information gathered from the tribal is useful for further researchers in the field of ethno-medico-botany, taxonomy and pharmacology .This study offers a model for studying the relationship between plants and people ,within the context of traditional medical system. The purpose of standardizing traditional remedies is obviously to ensure therapeutically efficacy .The value of using ethno medical information is to initiate drug discovery efforts .This study also generated a broad spectrum of information concerning medicinal plants used by tribal's .Due to lack of interest among the younger generation of tribal's as well as their tendency to migrate to cities for lucrative jobs, we face the possibility of losing this wealth of knowledge in the near future.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors are grateful to the local tribal traditional healers and rural herbalists of Adilabad district who whole heartily co-operated in sharing their knowledge and in helping the collection of the plant material for study. We also thank Department of Botany, Kakatiya University, Warangal, Andhra Pradesh, India for permitting to confirm the identified plant specimens with herbaria.

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Fig-1. Map showing the location of Adilabad district and study area (marked).

Table 1. Description of medicinal properties of plants used by traditional healers from rural areas of Adilabad District, Andhra Pradesh, India.

S. No	Botanical Name	Common Name	Family	Part Used	Medicinal Uses
01	<i>Abrus precatorius</i>	Gurijalu	Fabaceae	Seeds	Snake bite
02.	<i>Achalypa Indica</i>	Muripinda	Euphorbiaceae	Leaves	STDs & Jaundice
03.	<i>Achyranthes Aspera</i>	Uttareni	Amaranthaceae	Root	Tooth Ache
04.	<i>Ailanthus Excelsa</i>	Peddmamu Tree	Simaroubaceae	Root	Abscess
05.	<i>Aloe Barbadensis</i>	Aloe-Vera	Agavaceae	Stem	Skin Allergy & Ladies White Discharges
06.	<i>Alternanthera Sessilis</i> <i>Achyranthes Aspera</i>	Gungu Uttareni	Amaranthaceae Amaranthaceae	Root Root	Ladies White Dicharges
07.	<i>Aristolochia India</i>	Nalla Eswari	Aristolochiaceae	Root	Snake Bite
08.	<i>Azadirachta Indica</i>	Neem	Meliaceae	Leaves	Fever
09.	<i>Bambusa</i>	Veduru	Graminae	Leaves	Abortion
10.	<i>Butea Monosperma(L)</i>	Moduga	Fabaceae	Leaves	Pain
11.	<i>Calotropis Gigantea</i>	Jilledu	Asclepiadaceae	Flower	Cramps & Arthritis & Pains
12.	<i>Cassia Obtusifolia</i>	Thagerashe	Fabaceae	Leaves	Scorpion -Bite
13.	<i>Cassia Occidentalis (L.)</i>	Kassitha	Leguminaceae	Fruit	Sugar & Pains
14.	<i>Citrus Limon</i>	Limon Tree	Rutaceae	Fruit	Diarrhoea Dandruff, & Hair fall
15.	<i>Datura Metal(L)</i>	Erriummetta	Solanaceae	Leaves	Pains
16.	<i>Ecilptaalba</i>	Bhringraj	Asteraceae	Leaves	Blood Bleeding Skin Allergy, Hair fall, Dandruff
17.	<i>Ficus Religiosa</i>	Ravi	Moraceae	Stem bark	Hepatitis & STD's
18.	<i>Hemiessmus Indicus(L)</i>	Sugandi Pala	Asclepiadaceae	Roots	Tooth ache
19.	<i>Mimsa Puvica(L)</i>	Atti Patti	Leguminaceae	Leaves	Filaria, Blood Pressure
20.	<i>Momordica Charantia</i>	Bitter Gourd	Cucurbitaceae	Leaves	Jaundice & Diabetes,
21	<i>Moringa</i>	Munaga	Morigaceae	Root	Skin diseases
22.	<i>Ocimum</i>	Tulasi	Lamiaceae	Leaves	Skin Allergy

	<i>Tenuiflora(L)</i>				
23.	<i>Oroxylum Indicum</i>	Namale Tree	Bignoniaceae	Leaves	Pains
24.	<i>Pergularia Daemia</i>	Dustapu Teega	(Asclepiadaceae)	Leaves	Fever
25.	<i>Phyllanthus Amarus</i>	Nalla Usiri	Phyllanthaceae	Fruit	Ring worm, Jaundice & Fever
26.	<i>Phyllanthus Emblica</i>	Usiri	Phyllanthaceae	Fruit	STD's & Skin diseases
27.	<i>Pongamia Pinnata</i>	Kanugatree	Fabaceae	Leaves	Blood Pressure Paralysis & Pains
28.	<i>Prunus domestica</i>	Plum	Rosaceae	Leaves	Ladies White Discharges
29.	<i>Ricinus Communis (L.)</i>	Amudamu	Euphorbiaceae	Stem - Bark	Pains & Jaundice
30.	<i>Terminia Chebula</i>	Myrobalan	Combretaceae	Fruit	Cough & Diabetes,
31.	<i>Tinospora Cordifolia</i>	Tippatheega	Menispermaceae	Leaves	STD's, Diabetes, & Sugar
32.	<i>Trianthema portulacastrum</i>	Thella galijeru	Aizoaceae	Stem-Bark	Kidney disease
33.	<i>Tribulus terrestris</i>	Palleru	Zygophyllaceae	Leaves	Asthma
34.	<i>Trigonella foenumgraecum</i>	Menthulu	leguminosae	Leaves	skin diseases
35.	<i>Trolox procumbens</i>	Nallaalam (Gaddichamanthi)	Asteraceae	Leaves	Wound healing
36.	<i>Tylophora Indica</i>	Kakapalla	Asclepiadaceae	Leaves	Asthma
37.	<i>Vitex nigunda</i>	Vaavili	Lamiaceae	Leaves	Pains
38.	<i>Withania somnifera</i>	Ashwagandha	Solanaceae	Stem-bark	Fertility improvement of male
39.	<i>Xanthium strumarium</i>	Gokhru	Asteraceae	Leaves	Anti inflammations
40.	<i>Zingiber officinale</i>	Sonti	Zingiberaceae	Root	Asthma, Fever

Figure 2: Plant parts used for medicinal purposes and percentage of total medicinal species

Figure 3; Percentage of remedies used for various diseases

